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THE ROLE AND SIGNIFICANCE OF FILM DISCOURSE IN MODERN LINGUISTICS

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***Abstract:** the article discusses the role of discourse analysis in modern linguistics and its connection with cinematographic speech. It analyzes the social, cultural, and psychological factors reflected in language and communication, emphasizing the relevance of studying film discourse based on a linguocognitive approach. The author highlights the influence of cinema on human thinking, worldview, and information perception. The multimodal (visual, auditory, and emotional) nature of film discourse and its importance in uncovering semantic layers of meaning are examined. The study substantiates the scientific significance of analyzing discourse as a cognitive phenomenon that integrates language, meaning, and human experience.*

***Keywords:** discourse, film discourse, linguocognitive analysis, multimodal communication, cinematographic speech, linguistics, cultural concept, cognitive approach.*

The formation of new approaches in linguistics and the development of the scientific paradigm determined the need for a deep analysis of linguistic phenomena, including such concepts as "text" and "discourse". If in the first half of the 20th century the main attention of researchers was primarily focused on the structural features of

language, then from the second half of the century there was a shift in attention to the functioning of language in real communicative conditions.

In the field of modern linguistics, discourse analysis has become one of the most comprehensive methodologies. In particular, the profound influence of cinema on the thinking of society, the semantic layering of its language tools, has made it an independent object of analysis. Unlike ordinary text, film discourse has multimodal, interactive and connotative properties, in which, along with language, visual, auditory and emotional components are combined. Therefore, its study based on a linguocognitive approach is one of the current scientific issues.

The film form of art occupies a central place in a developed society, directly influencing people and their understanding of the environment. The simultaneous use of two means (acoustic and visual) in cinema distinguishes this art form from literature, music, radio, and others based on the use of a single method of communication. It is not surprising that cinema, as a work of art, has become the object of study in a number of disciplines, including linguistics.

In modern linguistic research conducted in the world today, cinematic speech is studied as a whole complex of linguistic, psychological, and social phenomena and as one of the types of speech. The areas of interest of such studies include the concepts of film discourse and cinematic text, types of cinematic speech and their classification, its functions, analysis of dialogues as a linguistic component of the film, etc.

At the beginning of the 20th century, cinema began to be studied from a linguistic point of view. M. Dynel notes that cinematographic speech differs from cinematic speech. Because cinematographic speech is aimed at studying cinematographic methods such as editing, sound design, camera work, which are outside the scope of linguistic research.

The phenomenon of discourse, in addition to linguistics, can be the object of research of many disciplines. Philosophy, sociology, and political science are among them. It should be noted that in recent years, from the point of view of

interdisciplinary consideration of language, the phenomenon of discourse has become unclear. It is precisely the multifaceted nature of the research that leads to the inexpediency of highlighting one conceptual definition. Discourse, "as a complex communicative phenomenon, includes a social context that gives an idea of both the participants in communication and the process of producing and perceiving a message, and is a complex unity of language form, meaning, and action". The cognitive-pragmatic orientation of applied research allowed scientists to characterize discourse as a cognitive phenomenon, since discourse influences the system of data transmission and information processing, as well as the actions of decoding and interpretation. We can see that researchers who have worked on discourse often rely on the definition given by N. D. Arutyunova: "Discourse is a text associated with extralinguistic, pragmatic, social, cultural, and psychological factors, a text obtained from the point of view of an event, and speech considered as a targeted social action, its component, speech embedded in life, participating in the interaction of people and their mechanisms of consciousness".⁴ This definition has become an active one due to the multiplicity of possible aspects of analysis and the consideration of the boundaries of the term discourse in other social spheres.

A complete cognitive analysis of the film tells us: "What worldview does the film instill in the audience? Which cultural knowledge will be activated?" Thus, linguocognitive analysis of cinema means viewing the film not just as a story, but as a "form that shows consciousness through language. "Through this approach, we reveal the conceptual worldview of the people or the author through the dialogues, images, and visual signs of the film being studied.

⁴ Arutyunova, N.D. 1990. Discourse. In the collection Linguistic Encyclopedic Dictionary. Moscow: Soviet Encyclopedia.

References

1. Arutyunova, N.D. (1990). Discourse. V sb. Linguistic encyclopedic dictionary. Moscow: Soviet Encyclopedia.
2. Van Dyck, T.A. (1989). Yazyk. Poznań. Communication. Moscow: Progress.
3. Kubryakova, E.S. (2004). Yazyk i znanie: Na puti polucheniya znaniy o zazyke. Chasti rechi s cognitive eye sight. Moscow: Yazyki slavyanskoy kultury.
4. Fowler, R. (1991). Language in the News: Discourse and Ideology in the Press. London: Routledge.
5. Kress, G. & van Leeuwen, T. (2001). Multimodal Discourse: The Modes and Media of Contemporary Communication. London: Arnold.
6. Lakoff, G., & Johnson, M. (2003). Metaphors We Live By. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
7. Iskandarova, D. (2018). "Linguistic and pragmatic analysis of film discourse". Issues in Uzbek linguistics, No. 2.
8. Karimov, O. (2020). "Cognitive Linguistics and Discourse: Theoretical Approaches". Philology and Language Teaching, No. 4.
9. Rizayeva, M. (2022). "Cinema Discourse and Multimodal Communication." Languages and Intercultural Communication, No. 1.